

Methods of Dispute Resolution Related to Cross-Border Green Contracts and Their Features

Davlatova Guliza Shavkat kizi

PhD student of Tashkent State University of Law

e-mail: gprimova97@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0003-7496-7628

***Abstract.** The development of cross-border green contracts aimed at sustainable development and an environmentally friendly economy is associated with a number of legal and practical problems, especially with regard to the resolution of emerging disputes. This thesis analyzes the applicable dispute resolution methods—negotiations, mediation, arbitration, and judicial proceedings— and the specifics of their application to international “green” contracts. Both traditional legal approaches and innovative ESG conflict resolution mechanisms are considered.*

***Keywords:** green contracts, cross-border transactions, dispute resolution, arbitration, mediation, sustainable development.*

The modern economy is in a phase of active transition to sustainable development. In this regard, the volume of cross-border green contracts is increasing, aimed at implementing environmentally sound initiatives, including projects in the field of renewable energy sources, reduction of CO₂ emissions, and sustainable land use. However, the specifics of these agreements, including the involvement of various jurisdictions and standards, lead to unique disputes that require specialized resolution methods.

To achieve the research objectives, methods of comparative legal analysis, the formal legal method, as well as empirical analysis of international arbitration precedents and decisions of international organizations (ICSID, UNCITRAL,

EBRD, etc.), are used. Only official sources were used, including international treaties, model rules, and scientific publications.

Green contracts are agreements aimed at implementing projects in the field of sustainable development and environmental transformation of the economy. Their structure may include provisions on reducing carbon dioxide emissions, using renewable energy sources, protecting biodiversity, and conserving resources.[1]

The features of cross-border green contracts are as follows:

participation by parties registered in different jurisdictions;

the need to comply with international agreements on climate and the environment;

the application of ESG standards and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is crucial;

involvement of government agencies, international financial institutions, NGOs, and local communities.[2]

Such multilateralism increases the risk of disputes related to both non-fulfillment of obligations and non-compliance with environmental standards.

Pre-trial procedures like negotiations and mediation take precedence at the beginning of the conflict.

Negotiations

Negotiations are the easiest and most economical way to resolve disputes out of court. In cross-border environmentally oriented contracts, they are especially important because the partners are interested in maintaining their reputation and long-term relationships. For example, in disputes over compliance with the conditions for reducing emissions or switching to renewable energy sources, the parties often prefer to start with discussions. However, the effectiveness of negotiations directly depends on good faith and a balance of power between the parties.[3]

It is often used as the first step to resolve misunderstandings, especially in situations where the dispute is of a technical or operational nature (for example, delayed delivery of solar panels or incomplete compliance with environmental standards).

Its advantages are the following: low cost, speed, and the ability to achieve a flexible solution. However, negotiations may not be effective if there is a significant conflict of interest.

Mediation

Mediation involves the participation of a neutral mediator who helps the parties reach a compromise. International commercial mediation received additional legal support after the adoption of the Singapore Convention (2019) and the UNCITRAL Model Law on Mediation (2018).[4]

Features of mediation in “green” disputes:

Take into account the environmental, social, and rights of local communities.

There should be flexibility in reaching a sustainable and balanced agreement.

There is a possibility of including environmental experts in this process.

Mediation is more structured. An independent mediator helps the parties to work out a mutually acceptable solution. The application of mediation is regulated by the UNCITRAL Model Law on International Commercial Mediation (2018), and the UN Convention on International Agreements Concluded as a Result of Mediation (Singapore Convention, 2019).

When parties have established business relationships and a shared desire to uphold their reputation in the “green” sector, mediation becomes particularly effective. In addition, mediation facilitates decision-making that takes into account local environmental interests and community rights.

International Arbitration

People recognize arbitration as the preferred mechanism for resolving cross-border commercial and investment disputes. This allows for neutrality and

confidentiality and ensures the international legal force of decisions (for example, by the New York Convention of 1958).[5]

Features of arbitration in the field of green contracts:

the analysis encompasses both contractual and environmental obligations;

involvement of ESG experts:

participation in the review of states, state-owned companies, or international organizations;

references to international agreements such as the Paris Agreement (2015) and the Aarhus Convention (1998).[6]

International arbitration institutions, such as the ICC, LCIA, ICSID, and UNCITRAL, are increasingly publishing rules or recommendations that take environmental aspects into account.[7]

Arbitration remains the main mechanism for resolving cross-border disputes, including in the field of “green” contracts. It provides a neutral, flexible, and institutionally structured platform.

Features of arbitration in “green” disputes:

The presence of environmental standards as part of contractual obligations (for example, compliance with ESG standards and IFC standards);

The possibility of participation of the state or international organizations as parties or third parties;

The presence of climatic and social components, such as respect for the rights of local communities or water resources, is crucial.

Many arbitration institutions adapt their rules to the specifics of sustainable development. For example, the International Criminal Court has published a report on the resolution of environmental and climate disputes.

LCIA and SCC take into account the principles of integrity and sustainability;

ICSID examines investment and environmental disputes between an investor and the state.

In practice, arbitrators increasingly analyze parties' legal and environmental obligations, including international agreements (the Paris Agreement, the Aarhus Convention, etc.).

The trial

Litigation is less popular in cross-border “green” agreements, but it remains relevant in the absence of an arbitration clause or in cases where one of the parties has obligations to the state.

Disadvantages of traditional litigation:

- limited jurisdiction;
- duration of the process;
- the complexity of implementing solutions abroad;
- lack of expert assessment of environmental aspects.

However, in some cases, for example, when considering claims for responsibility for climate change (climate litigation), the courts become an important platform. An example is the case of the Urgenda Foundation v. the Netherlands, in which the court ordered the state to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.[8]

Alternative accountability mechanisms

Within the framework of international financing of green projects (for example, infrastructure, green energy, REDD+ projects), non-conflict dispute resolution mechanisms are increasingly being used, including:

Accountability and complaint handling mechanisms:

CAO (Advisor to the Ombudsman for Regulatory Compliance) - at IFC (IFC), a structural unit of the World Bank Group;

IAM (Independent Accountability Mechanisms)—in the EBRD, ADB, and other international organizations.[9]

Their key features are:

- Handling complaints from local communities;
- Emphasis on harm prevention rather than compensation;

- Influence through termination or change of financing.

Though these mechanisms lack the authority to make judicial or arbitration decisions, they greatly affect the project's environmental policy.

These mechanisms allow local communities and stakeholders to file complaints about the environmental or social impacts of the project. Though these mechanisms lack the authority to make judicial or arbitration decisions, they greatly affect the project's environmental policy.

Hybrid forms and environmental tribunals

Modern practice also demonstrates the development of hybrid forms combining arbitration, mediation, and advisory functions. Along with this, environmental courts are being established in a number of countries (for example, in India, Brazil, and Kenya), specializing in environmental disputes, including cross-border aspects.[10]

These courts handle both internal and cross-border environmental disputes regarding the principles of sustainable development.

The analysis indicated that the resolution of disputes arising from cross-border green contracts requires an integrated, multi-level approach combining traditional legal instruments with innovative mechanisms focused on the principles of sustainable development.

Key findings:

1. Arbitration retains its dominant role as the main method of resolving cross-border commercial and investment disputes. Its advantages of neutrality, flexibility, and the ability to include ESG experts in the process make it particularly suitable for disputes related to green contracts.

2. Mediation and negotiation are highly effective in the early stages of conflicts, especially when the parties are interested in maintaining long-term relationships. We recommend their use in projects with a social or environmental component.

3. Judicial proceedings are limited in their applicability in cross-border “green” disputes due to jurisdictional issues and the length of the process, but they can be used in climate and human rights cases, especially in the context of states' obligations to citizens.

4. Alternative dispute resolution mechanisms developed by international financial institutions (CAO, IAM) are becoming increasingly important. They enable stakeholders, especially vulnerable communities, to enforce environmental and social standards outside of formal legal proceedings.

5. There is a tendency towards hybridization of procedures, which uses elements of arbitration, mediation, and mechanisms for monitoring compliance with ESG obligations. This phenomenon indicates the development of a special culture of conflict resolution in the field of green cross-border transactions.

6. The importance of the ESG and the SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) as substantive and legal standards is increasing. Increasingly, they are used not only as rules of recommendation but also as a source of obligations subject to legal analysis and resolution during a dispute.

To conclude, cross-border green contracts are becoming an integral part of the modern legal and economic system in the context of the global shift towards sustainable development and the increase in international environmental initiatives. However, the specifics of their content, the multilateral nature of the participants, and the binding to international environmental obligations create complex challenges in the field of dispute resolution.

The conducted research has confirmed that there is no universal way to resolve disputes in this area. The best mechanism depends on the dispute's nature, the parties' composition, the applicable law, the level of regulatory accountability, the state's role, and the project's environmental impact.

Practical recommendations:

1. At the stage of concluding a contract, the parties must clearly define the dispute resolution mechanism (arbitration, mediation, hybrid), provide for environmental standards as part of contractual obligations, and specify the applicable law, taking into account international agreements in the field of ecology.

2. In large projects involving international financial institutions, it is recommended to integrate accountability mechanisms (CAO, IAM), which will increase transparency and reduce the risk of socio-environmental conflicts.

3. It is advisable for arbitration institutions to develop special regulations and expert bases on ESG disciplines, which will provide a more in-depth analysis when considering “green” cases.

4. States should continue to harmonize national legislation with international standards for sustainable development and provide a mechanism for the enforcement of decisions related to cross-border green disputes.

As a result, cross-border green contracts require not only legal protection but also the formation of a stable legal environment in which dispute resolution will contribute not only to protecting the interests of the parties but also to achieving global environmental goals.

REFERENCES:

1. United Nations. (2015). *Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*. <https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>
2. European Investment Bank. (2021). *Green Bonds and Green Loans Framework*. https://www.eib.org/en/investor_relations/green-bonds-framework.htm
3. Susskind, L., & Ali, S. H. (2015). Environmental Mediation and the Green Economy. *Negotiation Journal*, 31(4), 381–398. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nej.12103>
4. United Nations Commission on International Trade Law (UNCITRAL). (2018). *Model Law on International Commercial Mediation and International Settlement Agreements Resulting from Mediation*. <https://uncitral.un.org>

5. United Nations. (1958). *Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards (New York Convention)*.

https://uncitral.un.org/en/texts/arbitration/conventions/foreign_arbitral_awards

6. United Nations. (2015). *Paris Agreement*.

https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/english_paris_agreement.pdf

7. International Chamber of Commerce. (2022). *Leveraging Dispute Resolution to Deliver Climate Justice*. <https://iccwbo.org/publication/leveraging-dispute-resolution-to-deliver-climate-justice/>

8. Dutch Supreme Court. (2019). *State of the Netherlands v. Urgenda Foundation (ECLI:NL:HR:2019:2007)*. <https://uitspraken.rechtspraak.nl>

9. Compliance Advisor Ombudsman (CAO). (2021). *CAO Policy: Environmental and Social Accountability for IFC and MIGA*. <https://www.cao-ombudsman.org>

10. Pring, G. W., & Pring, C. (2016). *Environmental Courts and Tribunals: A Guide for Policy Makers*. United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP).